

Project title: **Pathogen and Graphene**

Acronym: **PANG**

Cordis number: **690836**

Call for project: **H2020-MSCA-RISE-2015**

PANG publications dissemination report

Period covered by the report: from **01/01/2016** to **29/01/2020**

Periodic report: final report

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1. Academic outputs of the project

Researchers involved in PANG have published **45 publications** since the beginning of the project. Here is a list of all the project publications (ranked by decreasing order of publication date):

ARTICLE TITLE	JOURNAL TITLE	DOI	REPOSITORY LINK	PUBLICATION DATE
Mucin modified SPR interfaces for studying the effect of flow on pathogen binding to Atlantic salmon mucins	BIOSENSORS AND BIOELECTRONICS	10.1016/j.bios.2019.111736	https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-02367926/	27/09/2019 (under an embargo until 27/03/2020)
Neutrophil Extracellular Traps Initiate Gallstone Formation	IMMUNITY	10.1016/j.immuni.2019.07.002	https://opus4.kobv.de/opus4-fau/frontdoor/index/index/docId/12490	17/09/2019
NOX2 mediates quiescent handling of dead cell remnants in phagocytes	REDOX BIOLOGY	10.1016/j.redox.2019.101279	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6669319/	20/07/2019
Near-infrared light activatable hydrogels for metformin delivery	NANOSCALE	10.1039/C9NR02707F	https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-02368024/	25/06/2019
Efficient capture and photothermal ablation of planktonic bacteria and biofilms using reduced graphene oxide-polyethyleneimine flexible nanoheaters	JOURNALS OF MATERIALS CHEMISTRY B	10.1039/c8tb01676c	https://dial.uclouvain.be/pr/boreal/object/boreal%3A216364/datastream/PDF_01/view	27/03/2019

ARTICLE TITLE	JOURNAL TITLE	DOI	REPOSITORY LINK	PUBLICATION DATE
Interaction of 4 allotropic modifications of carbon nanoparticles with living tissues	THE UKRAINIAN BIOCHEMICAL JOURNAL	10.15407/ubj91.02.041	https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-02434281	20/03/2019
Aluminum oxide nanowires as safe and effective adjuvants for next-generation vaccines	MATERIALS TODAY	10.1016/j.mattod.2018.10.034	https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-01944313	28/02/2019
Reduced Graphene Oxide Embedded Polymeric Nanofiber Mats: An 'On-Demand' Photothermally-Triggered Antibiotic Release Platform	ACS APPLIED MATERIALS & INTERFACES	10.1021/acsami.8b14784	https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-01925513	30/10/2018
Autoimmune, rheumatic, chronic inflammatory diseases: Neutrophil Extracellular Traps on Parade	AUTOIMMUNITY	10.1080/08916934.2018.1519804	https://nbn-resolving.org/urn:nbn:de:bvb:29-opus4-112549	29/10/2018
A Novel Integrated Way for Deciphering the Glycan Code for the FimH Lectin	MOLECULES	10.3390/molecules23112794	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6278545/	28/10/2018

ARTICLE TITLE	JOURNAL TITLE	DOI	REPOSITORY LINK	PUBLICATION DATE
Active NET formation in Libman-Sacks endocarditis without antiphospholipid antibodies: A dramatic onset of systemic lupus erythematosus	AUTOIMMUNITY	10.1080/08916934.2018.1514496	http://www.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:1276175/FULLTEXT02.pdf	28/10/2018
Improved photodynamic effect through encapsulation of two photosensitizers in lipid nanocapsules	JOURNAL OF CHEMISTRY B	10.1039/C8TB01759J	https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-01913367	30/08/2018
Repeated photoporation with graphene quantum dots enables homogeneous labeling of live cells with extrinsic markers for fluorescence microscopy	LIGHT-SCIENCE & APPLICATIONS	10.1038/s41377-018-0048-3	https://europepmc.org/articles/pmc6106998	08/08/2018
Graphene-based nanomaterials in innovative electrochemistry	CURRENT OPINION IN ELECTROCHEMISTRY	10.1016/j.coelec.2018.03.016	https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-02189339/document	01/08/2018
Low amounts of bisecting glycans characterize cerebrospinal fluid-borne IgG	JOURNAL OF NEUROIMMUNOLOGY	10.1016/j.jneuroim.2018.04.010	https://opus4.kobv.de/opus4-fau/frontdoor/index/index/docId/10000	15/07/2018

ARTICLE TITLE	JOURNAL TITLE	DOI	REPOSITORY LINK	PUBLICATION DATE
Enhanced antibacterial activity of carbon dots functionalized with ampicillin combined with visible light triggered photodynamic effects	COLLOIDS AND SURFACES B-BIOINTERFACES	10.1016/j.colsurfb.2018.06.040	https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-01925065/	19/06/2018
Electrochemical Methodologies for the Detection of Pathogens	ACS SENSORS	10.1021/acssensors.8b00239	https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-02189343/file/Paper%206%20Electrochemical%20Meth.pdf	14/05/2018
Autoantibodies Recognizing Secondary Necrotic Cells Promote Neutrophilic Phagocytosis and Identify Patients With Systemic Lupus Erythematosus	FRONTIERS IN IMMUNOLOGY	10.3389/fimmu.2018.00989	https://repository.ubn.ru.nl/handle/2066/191427	07/05/2018
Reduced graphene oxide/polyethylenimine based immunosensor for the selective and sensitive electrochemical detection of uropathogenic Escherichia coli	SENSORS AND ACTUATORS B-CHEMICAL	10.1016/j.snb.2017.12.169	https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-01925128	01/05/2018
Graphene-based biosensors	INTERFACE FOCUS	10.1098/rsfs.2016.0132	https://europepmc.org/articles/pmc5915654	20/04/2018

ARTICLE TITLE	JOURNAL TITLE	DOI	REPOSITORY LINK	PUBLICATION DATE
Oligomannose-Rich Membranes of Dying Intestinal Epithelial Cells Promote Host Colonization by Adherent-Invasive E. coli	FRONTIERS IN MICROBIOLOGY	10.3389/fmicb.2018.00742	https://europepmc.org/articles/pmc5915571	18/04/2018
Aqueous medium-induced micropore formation in plasma polymerized polystyrene: an effective route to inhibit bacteria adhesion	JOURNAL OF MATERIALS CHEMISTRY B	10.1039/c7tb02964k	https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-01925084/document	13/04/2018
Graphene-based bioelectrochemistry and bioelectronics: A concept for the future?	CURRENT OPINION IN ELECTROCHEMISTRY	10.1016/j.coelec.2018.03.028	https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-02181952/document	29/03/2018
Heat: A Highly Efficient Skin Enhancer for Transdermal Drug Delivery	FRONTIERS IN BIOENGINEERING AND BIOTECHNOLOGY	10.3389/fbioe.2018.00015	https://europepmc.org/articles/pmc5818408	15/02/2018

ARTICLE TITLE	JOURNAL TITLE	DOI	REPOSITORY LINK	PUBLICATION DATE
Nucleic aptamer modified porous reduced graphene oxide/MoS ₂ based electrodes for viral detection: Application to human papillomavirus (HPV)	SENSORS AND ACTUATORS B-CHEMICAL	10.1016/j.snb.2018.02.065	https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-02189345/document	10/02/2018
Elevated serum lysophosphatidylcholine in patients with systemic lupus erythematosus impairs phagocytosis of necrotic cells in vitro	FRONTIERS IN IMMUNOLOGY	10.3389/fimmu.2017.01876	https://europepmc.org/articles/pmc5776078	17/01/2018
Nanomaterials for transdermal drug delivery: beyond the state of the art of liposomal structures	JOURNAL OF MATERIALS CHEMISTRY B	10.1039/c7tb02529g	https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-02189348/document	16/10/2017
Missing in action—The meaning of cell death in tissue damage and inflammation	IMMUNOLOGICAL REVIEWS	10.1111/imr.12569	https://opus4.kobv.de/opus4-fau/frontdoor/index/index/docId/10120	13/10/2017
Flexible Nanoholey Patches for Antibiotic-Free Treatments of Skin Infections	ACS APPLIED MATERIALS & INTERFACES	10.1021/acsami.7b12949	https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-01716582	28/09/2017

ARTICLE TITLE	JOURNAL TITLE	DOI	REPOSITORY LINK	PUBLICATION DATE
Functionalization of Reduced Graphene Oxide via Thiol–Maleimide “Click” Chemistry: Facile Fabrication of Targeted Drug Delivery Vehicles	ACS APPLIED MATERIALS & INTERFACES	10.1021/acsami.7b08433	https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-01804945/	14/09/2017
Selective isolation and eradication of E. coli associated with urinary tract infections using anti-fimbrial modified magnetic reduced graphene oxide nanoheaters	J. MATER. CHEM. B	10.1039/c7tb01890h	https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-01716569	01/09/2017
Altered glycan accessibility on native immunoglobulin G complexes in early rheumatoid arthritis and its changes during therapy	CLINICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL IMMUNOLOGY	10.1111/cei.12987	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC5543515/	04/08/2017
Neutrophil Extracellular Traps Open the Pandora’s Box in Severe Malaria	FRONTIERS IN IMMUNOLOGY	10.3389/fimmu.2017.00874	https://europepmc.org/articles/pmc5532516	28/07/2017

ARTICLE TITLE	JOURNAL TITLE	DOI	REPOSITORY LINK	PUBLICATION DATE
Advancements on the molecular design of nanoantibiotics: current level of development and future challenges	MOL. SYST. DES. ENG.	10.1039/c7me00048k	https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-01686819	10/07/2017
Inosine Released from Dying or Dead Cells Stimulates Cell Proliferation via Adenosine Receptors	FRONTIERS IN IMMUNOLOGY	10.3389/fimmu.2017.00504	https://europepmc.org/articles/pmc5406388	27/04/2017
On demand electrochemical release of drugs from porous reduced graphene oxide modified flexible electrodes	J. MATER. CHEM. B	10.1039/c7tb00687j	https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-01679631	20/04/2017
Photothermally triggered on-demand insulin release from reduced graphene oxide modified hydrogels	JOURNAL OF CONTROLLED RELEASE	10.1016/j.jconrel.2016.10.028	https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-01698205	28/01/2017
Transdermal skin patch based on reduced graphene oxide: A new approach for photothermal triggered permeation of ondansetron across porcine skin	JOURNAL OF CONTROLLED RELEASE	10.1016/j.jconrel.2016.11.029	https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-01693302	10/01/2017

ARTICLE TITLE	JOURNAL TITLE	DOI	REPOSITORY LINK	PUBLICATION DATE
Ménage-à-Trois: The Ratio of Bicarbonate to CO ₂ and the pH Regulate the Capacity of Neutrophils to Form NETs	FRONTIERS IN IMMUNOLOGY	10.3389/fimmu.2016.00583	https://europepmc.org/articles/pmc5145884	03/12/2016
Oxidative Burst-Dependent NETosis Is Implicated in the Resolution of Necrosis-Associated Sterile Inflammation	FRONTIERS IN IMMUNOLOGY	10.3389/fimmu.2016.00557	https://europepmc.org/articles/pmc5131011	01/12/2016
Antibacterial activity of graphene-based materials	J. MATER. CHEM. B	10.1039/C6TB01647B	https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-01693273	30/08/2016
Nanoparticles size-dependently initiate self-limiting NETosis-driven inflammation	PROCEEDINGS OF THE NATIONAL ACADEMY OF SCIENCES	10.1073/pnas.1602230113	https://europepmc.org/articles/pmc5056044	03/08/2016
Glycogen Dynamics Drives Lipid Droplet Biogenesis during Brown Adipocyte Differentiation	BIOLOGY	10.3390/biology5020014	http://europepmc.org/articles/PMC4929528	01/04/2016

ARTICLE TITLE	JOURNAL TITLE	DOI	REPOSITORY LINK	PUBLICATION DATE
Affinity of Glycan-Modified Nanodiamonds towards Lectins and Uropathogenic Escherichia Coli	CHEMNANOMAT	10.1002/cnma.201500229	https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-01679652	08/02/2016
Plasmonic photothermal cancer therapy with gold nanorods/reduced graphene oxide core/shell nanocomposites	RSC ADV.	10.1039/C5RA24662H	https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-01693288	17/12/2015

Open access to publications: As specified by the H2020 obligations, **all the publications of the PANG project were uploaded into an open access repository.** Some of the publications are also published in open access directly from the publishers' platforms.

2. Academic and social impact

In total, the publications of the project have received **512 citations**¹. Here is the list of the three most cited publications and the number of citations they received:

1. Antibacterial activity of graphene-based materials 10.1039/C6TB01647B **82**
2. Nanoparticles size-dependently initiate self-limiting NETosis-driven inflammation
10.1073/pnas.1602230113 **42**
3. Transdermal skin patch based on reduced graphene oxide: A new approach for photothermal triggered permeation of ondansetron across porcine skin
10.1016/j.jconrel.2016.11.029 **28**

The number of citations for each publication of the project is available in **Annex A**.

Citations are not sufficient to assess the impact of the project. Altmetrics data are a good way to broaden our approach of impact by providing us with some interesting information about publications impact on social networks (Twitter, Facebook), bibliographic reference manager (Mendeley), and mainstream tools (Wikipedia). Altmetrics score² offers a general approach of the social and academic impact of the project.

Social impact summary

Almetrics Score	27
Mendeley	801
Twitter	285
Press	22
Wikipedia	1

List of the five publications which had the most important impact and their detailed impact:

Title	Score	Mendeley	Twitter
Neutrophil Extracellular Traps Initiate Gallstone Formation	249	34	193
Repeated photoporation with graphene quantum dots enables homogeneous labeling of live cells with extrinsic markers for fluorescence microscopy	12,85	29	11
Neutrophil Extracellular Traps Open the Pandora's Box in Severe Malaria	10.5	31	19
Selective isolation and eradication of E. coli associated with urinary tract infections using anti-fimbrial modified magnetic reduced graphene oxide nanoheaters	10.1	21	2
Affinity of Glycan-Modified Nanodiamonds towards Lectins and Uropathogenic Escherichia Coli	9.75	17	1

Altmetrics data for each publication of the project is available in **Annex A**.

¹ Calculated from Dimensions data. (17/12/2019)

² Calculated by Altmetrics. (17/12/2019)

Annex A

Citations and social impact received by each publication (sorted by publication date descending order, 17/12/2019)

Article title	Number of citations	Score total	Mendeley	Twitter	Altmetric link
Mucin modified SPR interfaces for studying the effect of flow on pathogen binding to Atlantic salmon mucins	0	0.25	2	1	http://www.altmetric.com/details.php?citation_id=67892561
Neutrophil Extracellular Traps Initiate Gallstone Formation	8	248.99	34	193	http://www.altmetric.com/details.php?citation_id=65018021
NOX2 mediates quiescent handling of dead cell remnants in phagocytes	2	-	-	-	-
Near-infrared light activatable hydrogels for metformin delivery	0	0.25	5	1	http://www.altmetric.com/details.php?citation_id=62685641
Efficient capture and photothermal ablation of planktonic bacteria and biofilms using reduced graphene oxide-polyethyleneimine flexible nanoheaters	2	0.25	4	1	http://www.altmetric.com/details.php?citation_id=57886793
Interaction of 4 allotropic modifications of carbon nanoparticles with living tissues	1	-	-	-	-
Aluminum oxide nanowires as safe and effective adjuvants for next-generation vaccines	5	7	11	-	http://www.altmetric.com/details.php?citation_id=51319451

Article title	Number of citations	Score total	Mendeley	Twitter	Altmetric link
Reduced Graphene Oxide Embedded Polymeric Nanofiber Mats: An 'On-Demand' Photothermally-Triggered Antibiotic Release Platform	9	-	-	-	-
Autoimmune, rheumatic, chronic inflammatory diseases: Neutrophil Extracellular Traps on Parade	8	-	-	-	-
A Novel Integrated Way for Deciphering the Glycan Code for the FimH Lectin	1	5.3	11	8	http://www.altmetric.com/details.php?citation_id=50509024
Active NET formation in Libman-Sacks endocarditis without antiphospholipid antibodies: A dramatic onset of systemic lupus erythematosus	4	1.25	8	3	http://www.altmetric.com/details.php?citation_id=50503276
Improved photodynamic effect through encapsulation of two photosensitizers in lipid nanocapsules	non trouvé	0.25	5	1	http://www.altmetric.com/details.php?citation_id=47220926
Repeated photoporation with graphene quantum dots enables homogeneous labeling of live cells with extrinsic markers for fluorescence microscopy	8	12.85	29	11	http://www.altmetric.com/details.php?citation_id=46230106
Graphene-based nanomaterials in innovative electrochemistry	7	-	-	-	-

Article title	Number of citations	Score total	Mendeley	Twitter	Altmetric link
Low amounts of bisecting glycans characterize cerebrospinal fluid-borne IgG	2	-	-	-	-
Enhanced antibacterial activity of carbon dots functionalized with ampicillin combined with visible light triggered photodynamic effects	13	-	-	-	-
Electrochemical Methodologies for the Detection of Pathogens	23	8.25	77	13	http://www.altmetric.com/details.php?citation_id=44027752
Autoantibodies Recognizing Secondary Necrotic Cells Promote Neutrophilic Phagocytosis and Identify Patients With Systemic Lupus Erythematosus	4	2.1	10	5	http://www.altmetric.com/details.php?citation_id=40838631
Reduced graphene oxide/polyethylenimine based immunosensor for the selective and sensitive electrochemical detection of uropathogenic Escherichia coli	19	-	-	-	-
Graphene-based biosensors	14	0.5	22	1	http://www.altmetric.com/details.php?citation_id=39377052
Oligomannose-Rich Membranes of Dying Intestinal Epithelial Cells Promote Host Colonization by Adherent-Invasive E. coli	3	-	-	-	-

Article title	Number of citations	Score total	Mendeley	Twitter	Altmetric link
Aqueous medium-induced micropore formation in plasma polymerized polystyrene: an effective route to inhibit bacteria adhesion	0	0.25	12	1	http://www.altmetric.com/details.php?citation_id=37104481
Graphene-based bioelectrochemistry and bioelectronics: A concept for the future?	2	-	-	-	-
Heat: A Highly Efficient Skin Enhancer for Transdermal Drug Delivery	14	1	52	2	http://www.altmetric.com/details.php?citation_id=33249479
Nucleic aptamer modified porous reduced graphene oxide/MoS ₂ based electrodes for viral detection: Application to human papillomavirus (HPV)	14	1	30	1	http://www.altmetric.com/details.php?citation_id=40912169
Elevated serum lysophosphatidylcholine in patients with systemic lupus erythematosus impairs phagocytosis of necrotic cells in vitro	2	1.6	9	3	http://www.altmetric.com/details.php?citation_id=33452939
Nanomaterials for transdermal drug delivery: beyond the state of the art of liposomal structures	12	0.25	31	1	http://www.altmetric.com/details.php?citation_id=27538557
Missing in action—The meaning of cell death in tissue damage and inflammation	12	1.5	32	1	http://www.altmetric.com/details.php?citation_id=27483338

Article title	Number of citations	Score total	Mendeley	Twitter	Altmetric link
Flexible Nanoholey Patches for Antibiotic-Free Treatments of Skin Infections	9	7	25	-	http://www.altmetric.com/details.php?citation_id=33594984
Functionalization of Reduced Graphene Oxide via Thiol–Maleimide “Click” Chemistry: Facile Fabrication of Targeted Drug Delivery Vehicles	15	-	-	-	-
Selective isolation and eradication of E. coli associated with urinary tract infections using anti-fimbrial modified magnetic reduced graphene oxide nanoheaters	8	10.1	21	2	http://www.altmetric.com/details.php?citation_id=24611343
Altered glycan accessibility on native immunoglobulin G complexes in early rheumatoid arthritis and its changes during therapy	6	1.75	16	3	http://www.altmetric.com/details.php?citation_id=20210871
Neutrophil Extracellular Traps Open the Pandora’s Box in Severe Malaria	8	10.5	31	19	http://www.altmetric.com/details.php?citation_id=23845027
Advancements on the molecular design of nanoantibiotics: current level of development and future challenges	7	0.5	28	1	http://www.altmetric.com/details.php?citation_id=22536809
Inosine Released from Dying or Dead Cells Stimulates Cell Proliferation via Adenosine Receptors	2	0.75	17	2	http://www.altmetric.com/details.php?citation_id=20304664

Article title	Number of citations	Score total	Mendeley	Twitter	Altmetric link
On demand electrochemical release of drugs from porous reduced graphene oxide modified flexible electrodes	5	0.25	18	1	http://www.altmetric.com/details.php?citation_id=24041023
Photothermally triggered on-demand insulin release from reduced graphene oxide modified hydrogels	24	0.25	42	1	http://www.altmetric.com/details.php?citation_id=13161430
Transdermal skin patch based on reduced graphene oxide: A new approach for photothermal triggered permeation of ondansetron across porcine skin	28	0.25	37	1	http://www.altmetric.com/details.php?citation_id=14213933
Ménage-à-Trois: The Ratio of Bicarbonate to CO ₂ and the pH Regulate the Capacity of Neutrophils to Form NETs	26	1.75	21	4	http://www.altmetric.com/details.php?citation_id=14647829
Oxidative Burst-Dependent NETosis Is Implicated in the Resolution of Necrosis-Associated Sterile Inflammation	26	1.25	31	2	http://www.altmetric.com/details.php?citation_id=14330059
Antibacterial activity of graphene-based materials	82	-	-	-	-
Nanoparticles size-dependently initiate self-limiting NETosis-driven inflammation	42	3	51	-	http://www.altmetric.com/details.php?citation_id=20112082

Article title	Number of citations	Score total	Mendeley	Twitter	Altmetric link
Glycogen Dynamics Drives Lipid Droplet Biogenesis during Brown Adipocyte Differentiation	7	1	26	1	http://www.altmetric.com/details.php?citation_id=6494035
Affinity of Glycan-Modified Nanodiamonds towards Lectins and Uropathogenic Escherichia Coli	7	9.75	17	1	http://www.altmetric.com/details.php?citation_id=5989016
Plasmonic photothermal cancer therapy with gold nanorods/reduced graphene oxide core/shell nanocomposites	21	7	36	-	http://www.altmetric.com/details.php?citation_id=32236286